

Supplementary materials for the paper “On the Use of Large Language Models for Qualitative Synthesis”

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This document provides the supplementary materials for our study, “*On the Use of Large Language Models for Qualitative Synthesis*.” The study examines how large language models (LLMs) can support the qualitative synthesis (QS) stage of a systematic review (SR). We used a collaborative autoethnographic research method with two exploratory trials. Each trial was evaluated for methodological rigor and practical usefulness, and we interpreted the results in light of how LLMs are built and their current limitations.

Because comprehensive reporting for qualitative research [1, 2] exceeds the length limits of the main paper, detailed information on the study’s design, conduct, and data analysis is provided here.

The supplementary files are listed below, along with brief descriptions of their contents.

- [01 - Search QA QS LLMs.ods] Information from the search for related work on Qualitative Analysis (QA) and QS using LLMs conducted in Scopus. We did not find any work on LLMs for QS. The studies on LLMs for QA are reported in the 2nd Trial as the data set.
- [02 - Characteristics of Sound QS.ods] Intermediate stages of the process (based on thematic analysis) to distill the characteristics of a sound QS, including coding, grouping, and theme definition.
- [03 - 1st Trial.pdf] Detailed process and outcomes of the 1st Trial for both the manual synthesis and the LLM-assisted synthesis.
- [04 - 1st Trial assisted sup.pdf] Details of the interaction during the 1st Trial with the selected LLMs, including version information, all prompts, and responses.
- [05 - 1st Trial manual sup] Process and intermediate material from the reference manual analysis of the 1st Trial.
- [06 - 2nd Trial.pdf] Detailed process and outcomes of the 2nd Trial for both the manual synthesis and the LLM-assisted synthesis.
- [07 - 2nd Trial assisted sup.pdf] Details of the interaction during the 2nd Trial with the selected LLMs, including version information, all prompts, and responses.
- [08 - 1st Trial manual sup.pdf] Primary papers coded as the first stage of the manual analysis.
- [09 - Challenges for deductive approach.pdf] List of challenges used in the deductive stage of data analysis to identify the challenges we faced when using LLMs for QS.
- [10 - Evaluation of trial outputs.pdf] Details of the evaluations of the characteristics of a sound QS in the trial outputs.
- [11 - Data analysis supplementary information.pdf] Details on the traceability from the identified challenges back to the data

The transcripts of the trial follow-up meetings and the internal communications, all in Spanish, are not included in the supplementary material, but can be provided upon reasonable request to the first author.

References

- [1] O’Brien, B.C., Harris, I.B., Beckman, T.J., Reed, D.A., Cook, D.A., 2014. Standards for reporting qualitative research: a synthesis of recommendations. *Academic Medicine* 89, 1245–1251.
- [2] Tong, A., Sainsbury, P., Craig, J., 2007. Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ): A 32-item checklist for interviews and focus groups. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care* 19, 349–357.

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